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CHINA HORIZONS

DEALING WITH A RESURGENT CHINA

12 June 2025

Lianghui 2025 and Beyond: Between Economic Slowdown and Trump 2.0

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Funded by
the European Union

The project "Dealing with a Resurgent China" (DWARC) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101061700. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Abstract

In 2025, the so-called “two Sessions” (*lianghui*), namely the National People’s Congress (NPC) and the Chinese People’s Political Consultative Conference (CPPCC) annual meetings, took place as usual in early March. The 2025 Lianghui was dominated by economic issues: how to tackle the housing crisis, stimulate consumption and accelerate innovation is a context of growing protectionist barriers introduced not only by Trump 2.0 but many other countries. China’s economic slowdown has also fed social problems that the government tries to mitigate in supporting more actively but selectively the less privileged strata of the society. But it remains unclear whether the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) leadership can and actually want to change a growth model still largely led by exports and dominated by state-owned enterprises (SOEs). Some NPC and CPPCC members are asking for more openness to the outside world and more freedoms for private businesses, but it remains to be seen how much the CCP leadership will take their view into account: the new law promoting private firms enacted in April 2025 is far from convincing. In the new context social stability and political security have continued to be the priority, hoping that Chinese CCP-led regime remains more resilient than its major partners and competitors, e. g. the United States. Presented as a symbol of stability, Xi Jinping, 72, continues to dominate the political system and there is no visible sign that he is preparing his succession.

Key findings

- Innovation has become a top priority for the Chinese government.
- Efforts have been made to stimulate consumption, but their results have remained limited.
- Some NPC and CPPCC members are asking for more openness to the outside world and freedoms for private businesses.
- The CCP leadership needs to address more actively social problems, but social stability and political security remain the priority.
- The CCP-led political system continues to be tightly led and controlled by Xi Jinping and no successor can be identified.

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Part one: The *Lianghui*

In 2025, the *Lianghui* have been rather uneventful. The usual work reports were submitted to the NPC delegates. Simultaneously, CPPCC members debated about major policy orientations. Only one law was adopted, strengthening the role of people's congresses deputies at all levels as well as their relationship with the voters and presented as an important contribution to Xi Jinping's "whole-process people's democracy" (see below). But what dominated the *Lianghui* was the need to stimulate the economy and innovate in a context of growing economic frictions not only with the United States but with a larger number of trade partners.

One of the major documents presented to the NPC, on the first day of its annual meeting, was Premier Li Qiang's government work report.¹ While portraying China as a source of economic growth, stability, openness, peace as well "international fairness and justice" in stark contrast to Trump's America, Li's priority was clearly how to overcome the economic difficulties that had accumulated in the last few years, way before Trump started to introduce high tariffs.

The Premier, number two in the CCP top leadership, namely the seven-member Politburo Standing Committee, was quite candid. He acknowledged the headwinds that the Chinese economy had been facing: a "sluggish" consumption; "pressure on job creation and income growth" particularly for young university graduates; local government's "fiscal difficulties" -- read abyssal deficit, mainly caused by the housing market crisis; and "involutionary (*neijuan*) competition" in some industries (electric vehicle is probably the best example), where intense rivalry drives companies to up the ante in a self-defeating cycle of excessive investment that do not generate proportional returns. Chronic overcapacity and vicious price wars are the manifestation of this fierce competition.

Yet, the target Li set for growth was again, as in the previous year, "around 5%". In order to reach this objective, which he qualified as a "challenge", the Premier announced that the government's deficit ceiling would increase from 3% to 4% of GDP. The measures that are to be taken include the introduction in 2025 of a larger amount of ultra-long special treasury bonds: 1.3 trillion yuan (US\$180 billion) against 300 billion (US\$42 billion) the previous year. However, these bonds, which amount is far from being high in view of the size of the Chinese economy (around US\$18 trillion), will not only be used to stimulate consumption, a key declared objective of the Chinese authorities, but also to spur investment in infrastructure and research and development, underscoring how difficult it remains for the CCP to move away from its supply-side economic strategy. First used at the July 2024 Politburo meeting, *neijuan*-

¹ English version:

<https://english.news.cn/20250312/bb9eb168edfa4e669b00b8dff4f058ad/c.html> ; all the official documents released during this plenary session can also be found here: <https://npcobserver.com/2025/03/china-npc-2025-results-documents/>

style competition is now presented as an issue that requires self-discipline. On the side of the *Lianghui*, Luo Wen, head of China's State Administration for Market Regulation, declared that he would push for additional regulations.² Nonetheless, so far, "excessive competition" among firms has remained unabated as the ongoing price war between BYD and other electric car manufacturers has well demonstrated.

Overall, Li declared that the government would pursue "people-oriented macro-policies" that would place "a stronger economic policy focus on improving living standards and boosting consumer spending". He also mentioned some of the measures that would be taken, as enhancing household incomes, easing credit constraints and stimulating diversified consumption, but without giving any financial detail. Actually, these measures are rather limited and pointed, confirming policies decided earlier in favour of the disadvantaged, for example the decision made in September 2024 to give a one-off cash handout to those living in extreme poverty.³

In addition, mainly to address the property sector's slowdown, a total of 4.4 trillion yuan (US\$611 billion) in local government special-purpose bonds will be issues in 2025, compared to 3.9 trillion yuan (US\$542 billion) in 2024. Beijing will also issue 500 billion yuan (US\$69 billion) in special treasury bonds to replenish the tier-1 core capital of major state-owned banks. However, Chinese experts, as Ding Shuang, chief greater China economist at Standard Chartered Bank, have rightly pointed out that these amounts represent a modest stimulus package.⁴

Another important theme developed by the Premier in his report was the need for the government and the private sector to work together. In order to boost business confidence and put into policies the results of the extraordinary symposium held in February 2025 between Xi Jinping and key private entrepreneurs including Alibaba's Jack Ma and DeepSeek's Liang Wenfeng, Li promised that "profit-motivated law enforcement" against private companies would be curbed (see below the law on private business promotion) and "involutionary competition" would be rectified. He also promised to open more sectors to foreign investments, as the internet, cultural activities, the telecoms, healthcare and education. Nonetheless, the devil will be in the details, and it remains to be seen how much these sectors will be opened to non-Chinese firms. And more importantly, whether the Chinese economy can reach its 5% target in a domestic environment dominated by overcapacity and deflation and an international environment made of growing protectionism, confirmed a month later by Trump on 2 April Liberation Day, and even stagflation. Moreover, initial data point to a sharp decline of foreign direct investment in China: -10.9% to 320.8 billion yuan (US\$45 billion) in the first four months of 2025.⁵

² *South China Morning Post (SCMP)*, 6 March 2025, p. A3.

³ Liz Lee, "China to give one-off handouts to needy", *Reuters*, 26 September 2024, <https://www.reuters.com/world/china/china-give-one-off-handouts-needy-2024-09-26/>

⁴ *SCMP*, 6 March 2025, p. A2.

⁵ <https://tradingeconomics.com/china/foreign-direct-investment-yoy#:~:text=Continues%20to%20Fall->

The 2025 national budget highlights a number of priorities: spending on science will increase by 10% for a second year in a row to 398 billion yuan (US\$55 billion); “diplomatic endeavours” expenditures, which overall target the “Global South”, will be raised by 8.4% to around 64.5 billion yuan (US\$9 billion), up from a 6.6% increase in 2024; and the military budget increase was set at 7.2%, as in the two previous years and again higher than the GDP growth rate, to 1.78 trillion yuan (US\$247 billion).

The People's Liberation Army (PLA)'s objective is to become a “world-class” military by 2050. To justify this increase, Defence Ministry spokesman Wu Qian declared that “China has yet to achieve complete reunification and face one of the most complex security environments globally.” Probably alluding among several issues to corruption, he also admitted that the PLA still faced risks and challenges in meeting its modernisation targets, particularly its 2027 objectives, presented as “a journey of arduous, uphill tasks”.⁶

Some, as CPPCC delegate Chen Xianhui, a physics professor at the University of Science and Technology of China, have deplored that the R&D budget still “lagged behind other major powers as the US and France”,⁷

In a large public relations exercise, the heads of five government agencies (NDRC), ministries of Finance and Commerce, the central bank and the main securities regulator held a two-and-a-half-hour press briefing aimed to show that the Chinese government has the means to manage the potential external and internal economic risks that it faces as well as disposes of the additional “tools” to ensure growth. However, apart from a 1 trillion yuan (US\$139 billion) “guidance fund aimed to promote industrial upgrades and tech innovation and a 1.2 trillion yuan (US\$167 billion) boost for a larger tech independence, no other figure has been published,⁸ In other words, we are still waiting to see these additional “tools” being announced.

Foreign Minister Wang Yi's Press Conference

Foreign Minister and top CCP diplomat Wang Yi's 90-minute press conference was one of the most publicised moments of the *Lianghui*. Taking place on 7 March, it was a major public relations event, attended by hordes of Chinese and foreign journalists. It had a strong domestic political dimension in a sense that Wang Yi's comments also aimed to convey to the Chinese society that China is a stabilising force and its government “provided certainty in an uncertain world”. Claiming to promote multilateralism, respect international norms and give more voice to the Global South, Wang concentrated its attacks on Trump's United States presented as a bully and the major source of destabilisation and unpredictability.⁹

[Foreign%20Direct%20Investment%20in%20China%20fell%20by%2010.9%25%20year%20Don,rose%20by%2012.1%25%20to%2018%2C832.](#)

⁶ SCMP, 10 March 2025, p. A10.

⁷ SCMP, 6 March 2025, p. A3.

⁸ SCMP, 7 March 2025, p. A1.

⁹ SCMP, 8 March 2025, pp. A1-A3.

Flesh out whole process people's democracy

In order to give more substance to "whole-process people's democracy", the new form of socialist democracy introduced by Xi Jinping in 2019 and officially presented in a White Paper on 4 December 2021¹⁰, the NPC adopted a 34-article amendment to the Law on Deputies to the National People's Congress and to the Local People's Congresses at Various Levels. This amendment's major objective is to "ensure that people's congresses and their standing committees at all levels maintain close ties with the people". The amendment "adds provisions that lawmakers should, based on the principle of proximity, carry out activities to strengthen their connection with the public, listen to, and convey the opinions and suggestions of the people."¹¹ This revision also aims to strengthen the role of deputies vis-à-vis the people's congresses standing committees, the government, the courts and the procuratorates of the same level.

To explain the *raison d'être* of this amendment, Xu Dequan, an NPC delegate from Henan, stated that "understanding the aspirations [of the people], the difficulties they face and the problems they need resolving, deputies can thereby put forward high-quality proposals and suggestions that carry the interests of the people."¹²

The new law was adopted on 11 March on the day the NPC closed its annual session. Zhao Zhao, a deputy from Nanzhao county in Henan, was quoted as concluding that "The revised law standardizes our behaviour and protects our rights as deputies. It will greatly help us fulfil our duties."¹³

This reform indirectly underscores both the weak influence deputies have on public affairs and their loose relationship, to say the least, with the people who are supposed to choose and elect them at the grassroots, namely the township (*xiang*) and county (*xian*) levels. As it is well-known the whole election exercise is carefully organised and led by the CCP at every level. Yet, this reform is noteworthy, introduced in a context of deepening economic difficulties and frustrations, and should be seen as a measure aimed to consolidate social stability and political security. Obviously, whether

¹⁰ English version: "China: Democracy that Works",

http://english.scio.gov.cn/whitepapers/2021-12/04/content_77908921.htm

¹¹ Liu Caiyu and Zhang Han, "Draft amendment to Law on Deputies submitted to top legislature for deliberation", *Global Times*, 5 March 2025, <https://www.globaltimes.cn/page/202503/1329559.shtml>

¹² Ibid.

¹³ Cao Yin and Jiang Chenglong, "NPC deputies build broad consensus. Legislators urged to advance building of a strong nation", *China Daily*, 12 March 2025, <https://www.chinadaily.com.cn/a/202503/12/WS67d0653ba310c240449da377.html> ; cf. Also Chaohao Wei and Ying Sun, "Why Did China Amend Its Law Governing Delegates to People's Congresses?", *The Diplomat*, 10 April 2025, <https://thediplomat.com/2025/04/why-did-china-amend-its-law-governing-delegates-to-peoples-congresses/>

consulting the society more than before will contribute to reaching these aims remains to be seen.

A rather uneventful Lianghui

This was the only new law adopted by the 2025 NPC full session. No new nominations have been approved. The only unexpected development was the absence of Zhao Leji, the NPC Chairman, from the closing ceremony on 11 March because of a “respiratory tract infection”. Entrusted by Zhao, NPC Deputy-Chairman (and number two) Li Hongzhong presided over this ceremony.

This has been a rather uneventful NPC plenary session. Interestingly, the private sector promotion law was not discussed, let alone approved at the NPC plenary session. Released for public comments in October 2024, its first draft was discussed by the NPC Standing Committee (NPCSC) in December 2024 and February 2025 before being adopted by the same body in late April 2025 (see below). Made of 175 members, the NPCSC meets every two months; it appoints and removes most top officials of the central government, adopts most national laws and ratifies the large majority of treaties.

All the reports submitted to the NPC were approved without much surprise by a quasi-unanimity of delegates, with the usual exception of the Supreme People’s Court and the Supreme People’s Procuratorate reports, some delegates showing their concern about what they perceive as a lack of law and order.

Table 1 Votes in the 2025 NPC¹⁴

	Yes	No	Abstentions
Government Work Report	2,882	1	1
NPC Standing Committee Report	2,875	5	4
Supreme People’s Court Report	2,841	31	12
Supreme People’s Procuratorate Report	2,850	27	7
Delegates Law Amendment	2,881	3	0
National Economic and Social			
Development Plans	2,866	8	10
Central and Local Budget	2,857	17	10

¹⁴ “NPC 2025: Documents and Votes”, <https://npcobserver.com/2025/03/china-npc-2025-results-documents/>

Debates in the NPC and the CPPCC

Innovation

As it could have been expected, debates among NPC delegates and CPPCC members were dominated by innovation and artificial intelligence (IA) in particular. Just before the opening of the NPC, its spokesperson, Lou Qinjian, indicated that Deepseek, China's new IA instrument, showcased China's "innovation and inclusivity" in tech development, adding, probably alluding to the United States, that his country "will bridge the technological divide and prevent technological innovation from becoming a game for the rich countries and the wealthy".¹⁵ At the same time, CPPCC female delegate Qiao Hong, of the Academy of Sciences, told reporters that China had made significant progress in robot technology, particularly in humanoid robots.¹⁶ It is not a coincidence that Xi Jinping decided to personally address this question, grasping the occasion to send a positive signal to the private sector. In his discussion with NPC delegates of Jiangsu province, a major hub for electronics, machineries and car manufacturing, the CCP General Secretary reaffirmed both his support for private businesses and the need to better integrate scientific and technological innovation along with industrial innovation.

Among the interesting ideas made public during the NPC meeting was the prediction made by Liu Hanyuan, the founder and chairman of Tongwei Group, the world's largest solar cell manufacturer, that in 20 years, owing to the rapid expansion of renewable energies, China will not need to import crude oil anymore. In so doing, it will reach carbon neutrality 10 years ahead, in 2050 instead of 2060.¹⁷ It is far from certain, nonetheless, that this prediction is shared by everyone in the Chinese government.

Risks of AI

NPC and CPPCC members have been both proud of the progress made by China in artificial intelligence with the launching of DeepSeek in January 2025 and concerned about the fresh risks that such models generate. CPPCC member Qi Xiangdong, who is also Vice-Chairman of the All-China Federation of Industry and Commerce, asked for stricter regulations to better mitigate these risks, particularly AI-driven cyberattacks and cyberattacks targeting AI systems, indicating that 90% of the servers used by Chinese private firms lacked adequate security protection. To reduce misuse of AI technology, as academic fraud or deepfake scams, NPC delegate Li Dongseng proposed mandatory labelling of AI-generated content. Nonetheless, this proposal would be difficult to implement because of its potential cost and its negative impact on real-time AI applications.¹⁸

¹⁵ SCMP, 5 March 2025, p. A1.

¹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷ SCMP, 7 March 2025, p. A4.

¹⁸ SCMP, 7 March 2025, p. A6.

Military-civil fusion

Military-civil fusion in the industrial sector is nothing new: what is newer is the recommendation made to boost cooperation between the PLA and local governments. When meeting PLA and People's Armed Police NPC delegates, Xi Jinping emphasised again this objective, adding that the military and local governments should strengthen their cooperation to improve the quality and efficiency of military construction. More specifically, PLA NPC and CPPCC delegates have asked local governments to allocate more civilian emerging technologies to support the military. For example, NPC delegate Liu Shuwei, a lieutenant general in the PLA Air Force, said: "we need to innovate the model of transforming local emerging field resources into war [preparation]", and called for research centres to focus on key areas such as unmanned system and underwater and cyberspace warfare. Likewise, CPPCC member Lei Xun, an Air Force researcher, recommended the establishment of joint laboratories and shared test sites for the military and local governments, arguably to avoid duplication and reduce costs.¹⁹

Society issues

Among the society issues, the declining birth rate has caught the attention of NPC and CPPCC delegates. Jiang Shengnan, a writer and a member of the latter, proposed to abolish the "divorce cooling-off period", a very unpopular measure introduced in 2021 that compels couple to wait for 30 days before being allowed to finalise a divorce. In her view, this Civil Code clause has been a strong disincentive for young women to get married and have children. To increase the marriage rate, she also proposed to eliminate workplace age discrimination and overtime to give couples more time for their family.²⁰

Hong Kong and Macau

While the "one country, two systems" formula remains referred to by NPC officials, the priority is clearly to deepen Hong Kong and Macau's economic integration with the Greater Bay Area (GBA) or the whole Pearl River Delta zone, a region that includes Guangzhou and Macau, an initiative launched in 2019. On 4 March, NPC Spokesperson Lou Qinjian declared that "the central government would offer more support for the participation of Hong Kong and Macau in the development of the Bay Area".²¹ In his work report Li Qiang confirmed this priority: while Hong Kong and Macau should play a bigger role in deepening China's international exchanges, they should also "uphold the constitutional order" in other words the CCP leading role. Whether Beijing's additional support will help revive the two special administrative regions' economy remains to be seen. In any event, the CCP's pressure exerted on Li Kai-hsing's CK Hutchison Holdings not to sell its Panama Canal Port operations to BlackRock is a good indicator of Hong Kong's growing integration into the PRC.

¹⁹ *Jiefangjunbao* (PLA Daily), 10 March 2025, quoted by SCMP, 11 March 2025, p. A8.

²⁰ *Nanfang zhoumo* (Southern Weekend), quoted by SCMP, 7 March 2025, p. A4.

²¹ SCMP, 5 March 2025, p. A3.

Foreign Affairs

The NPC and CPPCC meetings were also the occasion to promote China's image and its stabilising role in the world economy in a context of growing uncertainty and volatility caused by US President Donald Trump's trade tariffs and restrictions to top technology transfers. NPC Spokesperson Lou Qinjian insisted on this point, emphasizing China's willingness both to “act as a participant and a leader” of South-South cooperation, deepening economic partnership with key partners of the Global South, and to strengthen its relations with the European Union (EU). Reiterating a well-known official statement, Lou added that China has “no fundamental conflicts of interest or geopolitical contradictions” with the EU.²²

All in all, during this year's NPC session, according to official data, 269 legal proposals were submitted, and over 8,000 recommendations were received from the near-3,000 delegates. Meanwhile, CPPCC National Committee members submitted 5,890 proposals. These various forms of participation are now presented as important features of China's consultative democracy or Xi's “whole-process people's democracy”.²³

Major Takeaways from the Two Sessions.

- The economy should continue to grow at a 5% rate but it is uncertain that China can reach this objective.
- Stimulate the economy and innovate are the government's top priorities.
- The NPC has once again shown that it is a rubber-stamp parliament.
- But more consultation of the deputies and of the public is now encouraged, as a way to consolidate social stability and political security.

²² SCMP, 5 March 2025, p. A3.

²³ Yuxuan Jia, “Transcript: Two Sessions Recap”, CCG Update, Center for China and Globalization, 16 March 2025, https://www.ccgupdate.org/p/transcript-two-sessions-recap?utm_source=post-email-title&publication_id=1216917&post_id=159166767&utm_campaign=email-post-title&isFreemail=true&r=fpp&triedRedirect=true

Quote

CCP General Secretary Xi Jinping reaffirmed both his support for private businesses and the need to better integrate scientific and technological innovation along with industrial innovation.

Part two: China since the Lianghui

Since the two sessions, the Chinese government has continued to introduce measures stimulating the economy and mitigating the impact of Trump's tariffs and restrictions. But since US-China trade negotiations first held in Geneva and later in London are far from being over, it is hard for Beijing to adjust its own economic strategy. To be sure, encouraging consumption remains the priority. Nevertheless, efforts have been selective and continued to concentrate on the most disadvantaged segments of the Chinese society as the rural poor and migrant workers.

In the same laps of time, the Chinese government has sent contradictory signals: one the one hand, it has finalised and enacted the law promoting the private economy; on the other hand, it has published a White Paper aimed at strengthening national security which is prone to convince foreign actors and investors to remain cautious. In any event, Xi Jinping remains at the top of the political system and has now embarked to purge not only his opponents but also some of his allies.

The new Private Economy Promotion Law

The Private Economy Promotion Law (*minyinying jingji cujin fa*) was approved by the NPCSC on 30 April 2025 and has taken effect on 20 May 2025. This 78-article law's objective has officially been introduced to overcome the "difficulties and challenges in terms of fair participation in market competition, equal use of production factors, obtaining investment and financing support and service guarantees, and protection of legitimate rights and interests."²⁴ However, according to experts' commentaries, this new legislation does not bring many more legal guarantees to a sector that, for ideological reasons, is not really called "private" (*sili*) but "people's operated" (*minyinying*).²⁵ It should be underscored that, among other things, the CCP has not only

²⁴ “国新办举行新闻发布会 介绍《中华人民共和国民营经济促进法》有关情况文字实录” (The State Council Information Office held a press conference to introduce the relevant situation of the "Law of the People's Republic of China on Promoting Private Economy), 8 May 2025, <chrome-extension://efaidnbnmnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://npcobserver.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/2025-PEPL-SCIO-Presser-Transcript.pdf>

²⁵ Jamie P. Horsley, "China's New Private Economy Promotion Law: Good Intentions Meet Weak Government Accountability", *NPC Observer*, 15 May 2025, <https://npcobserver.com/2025/05/china-private-economy-law-government-accountability/>

the right to set up Party cells in a “private firm” as soon as there are three Party members working in it but is entitled to be represented in its leadership, e. g. its board meetings.

True, additional guarantees have been included in the final text: For example, article 12 indicates that the state should ensure that private sector actors are “equally eligible under the law” to enjoy the state's policies to support development; article 61 prohibits entities (*danwei*) from unlawfully collecting fees from, imposing fines on, or apportioning (*tanpai*) financial burdens to private businesses. As Chinese law expert Jamie Horsley indicates, the new law “does require compensation of losses in a variety of contexts, including when policy commitments to or contracts with private businesses need to be changed in the public interest, but its scope appears to be limited to situations where specific commitments had been given to the specific private firm involved”.²⁶ Moreover, one of the unsolved problems is that private businesses are reluctant to litigate, since they hope, and actually need to maintain positive relationships with their regulators.

National Security White Paper

On 12 May 2025, the State Council's Information Office issued an unprecedented White Paper on “China's National Security in the New Era” (*Xin shidai Zhongguo guojia anquan*). Since this long document was not fully and immediately translated into English, it was clear that its major target is the country's domestic audience.²⁷ This White Paper first reiterates the point made by Wang Yi in his press conference on the side of the Lianghui: „China injects certainty and stability into a world of change and disorder”. It also confirms Xi Jinping's “holistic approach” to national security all the way from political, military and economic security to cultural, social and non-traditional security. According to this document, security entertains a dialectical relationship with economic development as well as reforms. While supporting globalisation, the Chinese government is keen to strengthen the resilience of the country's supply chain. Behind protecting the people, this White Paper's priority is the security of the regime and above all the CCP leadership.²⁸

Xi's Power Concentration and Purges

Xi Jinping continues to sit at the top of the CCP-state system. No sign of weakening or contestation has appeared within the Party although in the Chinese society Xi is indeed more and more criticised. After having eliminated his opponents and potential

²⁶ Ibid.

²⁷ Full White paper in Chinese:

http://www.scio.gov.cn/zfbps/zfbps_2279/202505/t20250512_894771.html ; English abstract : http://english.scio.gov.cn/whitepapers/2025-05/13/content_117871660.html

²⁸ Mathieu Duchâtel, “Reading the China's White Paper on National Security in the New Era”, *Expressions*, Institut Montaigne, 13 May 2025, <https://www.institutmontaigne.org/en/expressions/reading-chinas-white-paper-national-security-new-era>

challengers, he now targets some of his own allies and protégés, to keep consolidating power and allegiance.

On 28 November 2024, the Defence Ministry announced the suspension from his duty of Admiral Miao Hua, the Central Military Commission (CMC) member in charge of political work in the PLA. In late December, the removal of two former PLA generals from the NPC was confirmed: You Haitao, former deputy commander of PLA Ground Force, and Li Pengcheng, former commissar of the PLA's Southern Theatre Command Navy. The information published in late November 2024 by the *Financial Times* according to which Defence Minister Dong Jun was under investigation was not confirmed. But, after having replaced a year earlier Li Shangfu, now in detention for corruption, Dong has not yet been promoted to the CMC nor to the position of State Councillor, a senior rank in the State Council that defence ministers usually hold. In addition, Dong did not participate in early June in the Shangri La Dialogue, the annual international security conference held in Singapore every year. Finally, another even more senior military official, He Weidong, CMC second Vice-Chairman, is now in trouble. In April 2025, a month after he had called PLA delegates to the NPC on crackdown on "fake combat capabilities"²⁹, the *Financial Times* reported that he had been placed under investigation for corruption.³⁰ That said, it is hard to understand the genuine reasons of these purges: are they linked to corrupt practices or to political issues, for example a lack of allegiance to Xi or dedication to war preparedness, particularly vis-à-vis Taiwan and the US? At this stage, the question cannot be answered.

Purges are not limited to the PLA. In 2024, 8 members of the Central Committee, the 205-member powerful "Party's Parliament", were dismissed and another 8 are in trouble. Corruption is the usual reasons given for these purges. Nonetheless, they are also indicative of a growing sense of insecurity, an even a genuine paranoia, among the top Party leadership. These purges also show that power concentration in the hands of Xi – and according to some insistent rumours in the hands of Peng Liyuan, Xi's wife, as well, particularly regarding PLA top nominations³¹ – does not necessarily guarantee loyalty. Actually, Xi's endless anticorruption campaign has generated

²⁹ Amber Wang, "Chinese general calls for crackdown on 'fake combat capabilities' in the military", *SCMP*, 9 March 2025,

<https://www.scmp.com/news/china/military/article/3254722/chinese-general-calls-crackdown-fake-combat-capabilities-military>

³⁰ Demetri Sevastopulo, "Top Chinese general removed in latest Xi Jinping purge", *Financial Times*, 10 April 2025, <https://www.ft.com/content/8226e1d9-2e4a-4079-8f3c-2ae877ba5ba9>

³¹ Resham, "China's First Lady Peng Liyuan Bidding For A Bigger Role?", *StratNews Global*, 13 May 2024, <https://stratnewsglobal.com/world-news/chinas-first-lady-peng-liyuan-bidding-for-a-bigger-role/> ; Willy Wo-Lap Lam, "Peng Liyuan Rises Up the Ranks: Implications for Xi's Despotic Rule", *China Brief*, Volume 24, Issue 11, <https://jamestown.org/program/peng-liyuan-rises-up-the-ranks-implications-for-xis-despotic-rule/>

many frustrations and much antipathy towards China's strongman and the presidential couple.³²

Conclusion

The Chinese government is busy mitigating the economic slowdown and social frustrations that it is facing as well as stimulating innovation and consumption in a more contentious international environment. Private firms are now more openly supported by the authorities to play a bigger role as the way to stimulate the economy, create jobs and generate more consumption but they need to work closely with the Party-state. More consultation of the society has been encouraged at the grassroots, but the CCP remains the only decision-maker and regime security continues to be a top priority of Xi's China. Besides, constant purges within the PLA leadership as well as among civilian officials keep the bureaucracy in a state of fear that is not conducive to creative ideas or policy initiatives. Have we entered Xi Jinping's *fin de règne*? It is probably too early to say. Nonetheless, the question can sensibly be asked.

Make takeaways of China's domestic political situation since the Two Sessions:

- Encouraged to play a bigger role in the economy, private firms are supposed to receive better legal protections, but the impact of the private economy promotion law is far from being clear.
- National security and political security of the CCP-led regime are more crucial than ever.
- Political purges have continued, now affecting Xi's own allies, both in the PLA and the Party's apparatus.
- Xi's personal power has not been questioned, let alone jeopardised; on the contrary, he remains the final decision-maker and his wife, Peng Liyuan, seems to play a bigger role in politics, particularly in the PLA.

³² Wu Guoguang, "Xi Jinping's Purges Have Escalated. Here's Why They Are Unlikely to Stop", *ChinaFile*, 25 February 2025, <https://www.chinafile.com/reporting-opinion/viewpoint/xi-jinpings-purges-have-escalated-heres-why-they-are-unlikely-stop>

Funded by
the European Union

The project "Dealing with a Resurgent China" (DWARC) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101061700. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.